

Framingham Risk Assessment of Coronary Heart Diseases in Selected Area of Dhaka City: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: A substantial number of reports indicate that the prevalence of coronary heart disease has increased both in developed and developing countries. This cross-sectional study was conducted in Mirpur area of Dhaka city from July 2010 to June 2011 with an aim to estimate the 10-year risk of coronary heart disease by Framingham coronary heart disease risk assessment tool.

Methods: A total of 140 males and 207 females between 30 and 74 years of age were selected purposively from three Government colonies. Data were collected by interview, blood pressure measurements and laboratory analyses. Original Framingham risk score model was used to get percentage risk of the individuals.

Results: Three fifth of the respondents were females and more than two fifth (44%) were between age 30 and 39 years. Females were mostly in non paid occupations (83.6%) and males were in paid occupations (93.6%) ($p < 0.001$). Two third respondents had monthly family expenditure of 10,000-19,000 taka. More than two fifth (45.7%) male participants were current smoker ($p < 0.001$), around one fourth of the total participants were diabetic, two-fifth proportion had hypertension and most of them (87%) had dyslipidemia where females were higher in proportion ($p < 0.01$). Around three fourth of the participants had low risk (<10% CHD risk in 10 years), followed by more than one fifth (21.6%) in the intermediate risk (10-20 % CHD risk in 10 years) and around three percent had high risk (>20% CHD risk in 10 years). Males were in higher risk than females ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: It is necessary to continue further research in different socio-economic people of the country and effective intervention strategy against coronary heart disease to reduce the health risk of the population. Follow up study to check the prediction capability of the tool is recommended.

Key words: Framingham tool, 10-year CHD risk, risk prediction, Bangladesh

(*JNHFB 2018; 7 : 12-17*)

Introduction

Incidence and prevalence of coronary heart disease (CHD), particularly myocardial infarction (MI), has increased in most regions of the world over the last decades¹. Now it is the leading cause of death worldwide. It is on the rise and has become a true pandemic that respects no border. A substantial number of reports indicate that the prevalence of CHD has increased both in the developed and in the developing countries. An estimated 17.1 million people died from

cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) in 2004, representing 29% of all global deaths. Of these deaths, an estimated 7.2 million were due to coronary heart disease. Low- and middle-income countries are disproportionately affected: 82% of CVD deaths take place in low- and middle-income countries and occur almost equally in men and women. By 2030, almost 23.6 million people will die from CVDs, mainly from heart disease. These are projected to remain the single leading causes of death and the largest will be in the South-East Asia Region². Estimates on mortality due to coronary heart disease according to the region indicate that developing countries contribute with a greater part of the overall burden of mortality due to the disease than

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developed countries³. Deaths from coronary heart disease in India rise from 1.17 million in 1990 to 1.59 million in 2000 and 2.03 million in 2010⁴. Most developing countries are experiencing the double burden of diseases resulting in inadequate attention to both categories of disease. Of all coronary heart disease patient who die within 28 days after the onset of symptoms, about two third die before reaching hospital. This highlights not only the need for early recognition of warning signs of a heart attack, but also the need for prevention⁵. The strategy for primary prevention in people with no history of CVD is to estimate the absolute risk of a vascular event and to take appropriate action according to that level of risk. But currently there is no accepted method to identify people who are at high risk of developing coronary heart disease in many countries⁶. The recognition of risk factors for coronary heart disease is one of the major achievements of coronary heart disease epidemiology in the 20th century. CHD prevention has focused on the identification of individuals at high risk by combining individual risk factors and reducing overall absolute cardiovascular risk. Effective primary prevention thus requires an assessment of risk to categorize patients for selection of appropriate interventions. Major coronary risk factors are smoking, hypertension, dyslipidemia, diabetes and obesity. Other factors that are considered to be important are fat distribution, family history of premature CHD and lifestyle risk factors⁷. To this effect, the risk assessment defined by the Framingham Study researchers was a great leap forward. The Framingham Heart Study is the oldest and probably the most informative of all prospective studies of cardiovascular risk⁸.

Latest survey on cardiovascular diseases carried out in Bangladesh showed prevalence of hypertension in adult population about 20-25% and ischaemic heart disease in adult population about 10%⁹. Other risk factors like smoking prevalence is 53.6%¹⁰. The Framingham Risk Score was initially designed to predict fatal and non-fatal coronary heart disease in a North American population, but this predictive model has also proven its reliability in different ethnic group¹¹. So, from the above discussion it has been observed that Bangladesh is experiencing different risk factors which may precipitate high burden of coronary heart disease. However, Effective prevention strategies for CHD do exist¹². We require specific data on the current situation so that priorities can appropriately be set and targeted. The current study aims to assess the 10 year CHD risk of the urban population by Framingham Risk Score tool and develop a baseline database.

Materials and Methods:

The current study was a population based cross-sectional study which was conducted from July, 2010 to June, 2011 in three government colonies in Mirpur area of Dhaka city. Study was focused on the assessment of 10-year coronary heart disease risk of urban population of Bangladesh at a single point of time. The government colonies are the

residential area where a large number of families of government service holders from the different district live in. A total of 347 participants of both sexes between 30 and 74 years of age participated in the study. They were the usual resident of the flat and who complied with the instruction of the study e.g. 12 hours overnight fasting was considered eligibility for the study. We excluded pregnant woman and known case of CVD cases from the study.

All necessary administrative approvals were obtained from the appropriate authorities before commencement of the study. Acquiescence to conduct this study was also obtained from the local committee of target population. The field assistants invited the potential participants for informed consent. The interviews and measurements were done at the household level. A referral card was given to the participant and requested to attend the Bangladesh Institute of Health Sciences (BIHS) hospital for blood sample collection on a pre-arranged date after an overnight fast for about 12 hours. During the data collection every participant was explained about the necessity of the fasting state for minimum of 12 hours prior to the test.

The participants were interviewed face to face for some general information and life style data through a pre-tested questionnaire. The interview took 30 to 40 minutes maximum including the informed consent process, blood pressure measurement and general baseline data. The participants were asked about their smoking status and alcohol consumption. The participants were also asked about their medical history such as, diabetes and hypertension.

Blood pressure was measured in sitting position, with calf at the level of the heart. After 10 minutes of rest a second reading was taken. Recorded Korotkoff sound I (the first sound) and V (the disappearance of sound) denoted the systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), respectively (according to WHO-ISH). If the difference between two readings was more than 5 mm of Hg, a third reading was taken.

On pre-scheduled date and time after coming to BIHS the fasting state of the participant was confirmed and 5 cc of venous blood was collected with aseptic precaution. The participant was given 75 gm glucose in 250 ml of water and advised to drink within 3- 5 min. Two hours after glucose administration 3 cc venous blood was again collected. It was ensured that the participant was not doing any physical activity and taking any food in this time period. After 30 minutes blood samples were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm to obtain plasma and serum. Separated plasma and serum was preserved in a freezer (-27° C) for future biochemical analysis.

Fasting and 2hours after plasma glucose, triglyceride, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol were analyzed by the Biomedical Research Group (BMRG) of Bangladesh Institute of

Research and Rehabilitation in Diabetes, Endocrine and Metabolic Disorders (BIRDEM). Glucose (fasting and 2 hr after glucose) was measured by Glucose Oxidase (GOD-PAP) method (Randox Laboratories Ltd., UK). Total cholesterol was measured by enzymatic colorimetric (cholesterol oxidase /peroxidase) method using reagents from Randox Laboratories, UK. Serum triglyceride was estimated by enzymatic colorimetric (GOD-PAP) method using reagents from Randox Laboratories, UK. Serum high density lipoprotein (HDL-C) was measured by enzymatic colorimetric (cholesterol CHOD-PAP) method (RANDOX Laboratories, UK). All the estimations were carried out in an autoanalyzer Hitachi 704. The LDL- Cholesterol level in serum was calculated by using Friedewald formula [Friedewald WT 1972].

The Formula is as follows:

$$\text{LDL- Cholesterol} = \text{Total cholesterol} - [1/5 (\text{Triglycerides}) + \text{HDL cholesterol}]$$

After collection, data were checked thoroughly for consistency and completeness. Data were initially checked on the day of collection to exclude any error or inconsistency or incompleteness. Data were categorized and coded during entry into the SPSS software. The estimation of coronary heart disease risk was based on the original equation of the Framingham heart study in the version published by Wilson et al., 1998. For every person Framingham risk score was calculated from risk factors obtained from the Framingham risk score table. Then the scores were simply added up to get a total risk score. Using Framingham table, the risk score equates to a percentage risk that the person might develop coronary heart disease on next 10 years. Then from another table, the percentage risk was categorized into low, intermediate and highest risk group.

Statistical associations between categorical variables were tested using χ^2 test and mean difference by t-test. All p- values presented were two tailed. The statistical tests were considered significant at a level of 5% (0.05). All the statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 22 version software.

Results:

The study included 347 participants between 30 and 74 years where females were 60 percent. Table-1 shows half of the females (50.2%) were within the age group of 30 to 39 years when about one third of the male (35.7%) were in this range. In 40-49 year age group both sexes were almost equal in proportion. Males were, on average, 3 years older than females and their mean difference were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Females were mostly in non-paid occupations (83.6%) whereas most of the males were in paid occupations (93.6%). Occupations between two genders varied significantly ($p < 0.001$). Mean monthly family expenditure of males and females were 16,426 taka. Two third of the respondents (64.8%) had family expenditure of 10,000-19,000 taka, one fourth (27.7%) had $\geq 20,000$ taka and around eight percent had $< 10,000$ taka which was almost equally distributed between males and females.

Table-1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

Characteristics	Male (n=140)		Female (n=207)		Total (n=347)		p
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Age of the respondents (years)							
30-39	50	(35.7)	104	(50.2)	154	(44.4)	0.002
40-49	46	(32.9)	70	(33.9)	116	(33.4)	
50-59	38	(27.1)	24	(11.6)	62	(17.9)	
≥ 60	6	(4.3)	9	(4.3)	15	(4.3)	
Mean \pm SD	43.8 \pm 9.02		40.2 \pm 9.06		41.6 \pm 9.20		0.03
Occupation							
Non-paid occupation	9	(6.4)	173	(83.6)	182	(52.5)	0.001
Service	126	(90.0)	33	(15.9)	159	(45.8)	
Business	5	(3.6)	1	(0.5)	6	(1.7)	
Monthly family expenditure (in taka)							
<10,000	8	(5.7)	18	(8.7)	26	(7.5)	ns
10,000-19,000	90	(64.3)	135	(65.2)	225	(64.8)	
$\geq 20,000$	42	(30.0)	54	(26.1)	96	(27.7)	
Mean \pm SD	16600.0 \pm 3683.1		16309.1 \pm 4537.9		16426.5 \pm 4210.8		ns

In relation to the other CHD risk factors (Table-2), more than two fifth (45.7%) male participants were current smoker where gender varied significantly ($p < 0.001$). Around one fourth of the total participants were diabetic which include known cases and newly diagnosed cases. Around two fifth of the respondents were hypertensive which comprises past diagnosed and newly diagnosed cases. In blood lipid distribution, most of the participants were in the dyslipidemia group where females were higher in proportion. Lipid differ between genders significantly ($p < 0.01$).

Table-2: Distribution of the respondents in relation to different CHD risk factors

Characteristics	Male (n=140)		Female (n=207)		Total (n=347)		p
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Smoking status							
Current smoker	64	(45.7)	0	(0)	64	(18.4)	0.000
Others (former + occasional)	76	(54.3)	207	(100)	283	(81.6)	
Diabetes							
Non-diabetic	106	(75.7)	159	(76.8)	265	(76.4)	ns
Diabetic	34	(24.3)	48	(23.2)	82	(23.6)	
Blood Pressure							
Normal	79	(56.4)	126	(60.9)	205	(59.1)	ns
Hypertensive	61	(43.6)	81	(39.1)	142	(40.9)	
Blood lipid							
Normal	29	(20.7)	16	(7.7)	45	(13.0)	0.001
Dyslipidemia	111	(79.3)	191	(92.3)	302	(87.0)	

In Figure-1, around three fourth of the participants had low risk (<10% CHD risk in 10 years), followed by one fifth (21.6%) in the intermediate risk (10-20 % CHD risk in 10 years) and around three percent had high risk (>20% CHD risk in 10 years). Risk categories significantly differ between the sexes ($p<0.001$). High risk was most commonly found in participants with advanced age, and was more common in men (5.7%) than women (0.5%). In other risk categories, more than one third(34.3%) male were in intermediate risk and most of the females (86.5%) were in low risk.

Figure-1: Distribution of the respondents in relation to 10-year CHD risk categories

Discussion:

The general objective of this study was to assess the 10-year coronary heart disease (CHD) risk among the urban population who were not diagnosed as cardiac patient by using original Framingham CHD risk score model. Framingham Risk Score give an indication of the likely benefits of prevention, they are useful for both the individual patient and for the clinician in helping decide whether lifestyle modification and preventive medical treatment, and for patient education, by identifying men and women at increased risk for future cardiovascular events¹³. Framingham Heart Study used age, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein (HDL-C) and blood pressure as continuous variable and in contrast to dichotomous variable (yes/no) which included smoking and diabetes. The point score table was sex specific¹⁴.

After the calculation of the point table this study found that around three fourth of the participants had low risk (<10% CHD risk in 10 years), followed by more than one fifth (21.6%) in the intermediate risk (10-20 % CHD risk in 10 years) and around three percent had high risk (>20% CHD risk in 10 years). Risk categories significantly differ between the sexes ($p<0.001$). Males were in more risk than females in comparison to all 10-year CHD risk categories. Study also assessed that high risk was most commonly found in men (5.7%) than women (0.5%) and similarly in intermediate risk (men were 34.3% and women were 13%). It would be inappropriate to state that men were on six

percent high risk. Rather, a correct interpretation would be to say that, given 100 similar individuals, we expect that 6 will experience an event in the next 10 years and 94 will not. The individuals particularly in the intermediate risk group can assist in modifying base risk estimate. It is also important to recognize that a “low-risk” risk estimate (eg, <10%) does not mean “no risk,” particularly in the context of longer time horizons than 10 years. If the patient is expected to live >10 years, his or her 10-year risk estimate will perforce increase over time, and any adverse levels of risk factors present at younger ages may cause marked elevations in lifetime risks for CHD¹⁵. The study was rather new in Bangladesh and quite unique; therefore, it is difficult to make a scientific comprehension of this high proportion risk of CHD. In a population based cross-sectional study on different ethnic people in South London, they found South Asians (Bangladeshi, Indian and Pakistani) are on more risk (>12%) than South African origin¹⁶. In a cohort study at Bangalore and Mumbai of India, they found 61% males were in high risk followed by females in lower proportion (39%). In Newcastle Heart project, they predict risk on South Asian population and found 67% of 10-year coronary heart disease risk in Asian women¹⁷.

The study was conducted on 140 males and 207 females of 30 to 74 year age who had no history of coronary heart disease. Age is a very important characteristic for this study because in Framingham risk scoring system point score increase with age. Age may be the only major risk factor that does not cause CHD by directly promoting atherosclerosis. However, accumulation of atherosclerotic plaques in CHD progresses overtime, and the probability of developing an adverse coronary event is a function of the total coronary plaque burden. Thus, increased age increases the risk of developing more severe CHD. Most new onset CHD in both men and women occurs after the age of 65 years, and almost 85 percent of all deaths due to CHD are recorded among people 65 years of age and older¹⁸. In Bangladesh >65 years populations is only 4%¹⁹ and as the participants of this study were the residence of Govt. colonies, it might be the cause of higher participants (78%) of below 50 years of age. Female participation was higher (60%) because females were more co-operative and probably more health conscious than male.

Smoking is another important variable for this study. All most all female participants were never smoker and more than two fifth males were current smoker. A case control study in a tertiary level hospital of Bangladesh found association of risk factor smoking and smokeless tobacco with CHD²⁰. According to Global Adult Tobacco survey (GATS) of Bangladesh report, 44.7% of men and 1.5% of women are currently smoke tobacco. In New Castle Heart project they found 58% male smokers and only 3 % female smokers of Bangladeshi origin in high risk CHD group²¹. These reports support our study findings and it might be one of the causes of males were on higher risk than females.

Blood glucose was another important risk factor for this study. Around one fourth of the respondents were diagnosed as diabetic cases. Framingham Risk scoring table provides 2 points for male diabetic and 4 points for female diabetic cases. In a similar study, the seven-year incidence of first MI among people with type 2 DM was 20.2%, which was significantly higher than in people who did not have DM (3.5%). The mortality rate attributed to CHD among people who had DM but no history of MI (15.4%) was as high as among high-risk groups of people without DM who had a prior MI (15.9%). Among people who had DM but no previous MI, the mortality rate due to CVD was 7.5 times greater than in people without DM and no previous MI²². So, there is strong evidence to suggest that diabetes is a major risk factor for CHD and this study also reflects that by its result.

Current study explores that around two fifth of the respondents were hypertensive. More importantly, Framingham and other epidemiological studies, demonstrated that systolic and diastolic blood pressure has a continuous, independent, graded, and positive association with cardiovascular outcomes²³. According to National Heart Foundation Hospital & Research Institute prevalence of hypertension is 20 to 25%. In this study higher percentage of hypertensive participant might be the cause of higher proportion of participant above low 10-year CHD risk level.

Most of the respondents (87%) were dyslipidemic and the main reason was due to most of them had low HDL level. In Framingham scoring system points are given for different level of cholesterol and HDL which are sex specific. It has been estimated that the benefits of reducing serum cholesterol for CHD risk are age-related. A 10% reduction in serum cholesterol produces a drop in CHD risk of 50% at age 40, 40% at age 50, 30% at age 60, and 20% at age 70²⁴. To avoid metabolic syndrome related CHD risk factors it is recommended to keep HDL-C for men \geq 40 mg/dl and for women \geq 50 mg/dl. In Framingham Score model there were 2 points for $<$ 35 mg/dl of HDL-C for men and 5 points for women which decrease with the rise of HDL-C level. Although the risk of developing CHD is very low when the serum LDL cholesterol level is below 100 mg/dl, Combination of several risk factors usually provides a more comprehensive picture of the overall risk. Thus, men aged 45 to 65 years are at an increased risk of developing CHD when their total serum cholesterol level is $<$ 240 mg/dl and/or their LDL cholesterol levels are $>$ 160 mg/dl²⁵. In Framingham Score model there are points for the different level of LDL-C which is sex specific. Points are calculated either for LDL-C or for HDL-C of the participant. The role of triglycerides as an independent risk factor for CHD has been always controversial and, although some consistent evidence has been put forward, there are some doubts about the independent nature of this relationship²⁶. From the above study findings it can be concluded that dyslipidemia might be one of the major risk factor for high proportion of 10-year CHD risk.

Individuals with 10-year risks $>$ 20% are recommended for immediate clinical consultation to reduce their risk. In participants with intermediate risk (10% to 20%), the recommendation is either to start drug therapy or to pursue other noninvasive testing for further risk stratification. Lower-risk subjects are typically not recommended for drug therapy, but for lifestyle modification as appropriate.

Conclusion

As the research is rather new in Bangladesh, it is necessary to follow up study to check the prediction capability of the tool and continue further research in different socio-economic people of the country and effective intervention strategy against coronary heart disease to reduce the health risk of the population.

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